
A study of modern and early traditional (Siddha) medicine systems

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Abstract : Medicine is the art and science of treating diseases .The rise and dominance of modern medicine began in the 1800s in Western countries. Modern medicine uses health sciences, biomedicine, biomedical research, and medical technology to diagnose and treat injuries and diseases.This type of treatment is often done through medications, surgery, and other treatments. Ancient medicine existed before modern medicine, and was unique to that society.Prehistoric medicine included plants, animal organs, and minerals Ancient medical systems include Siddha medicine of the Indian subcontinent.Modern Medicine has so Many Divisions , at the same time Siddha medicine also has Common Medicine ,Special Medicine (varma). Modern Medicine has some Treatment methods in siddha medicine 32type internal therapy and 32 type of extranal therapy .**Aim**This study is to compare the modern medicine and Siddha medicine. **METHODOLOGY** This study compiles Data on modern medicine and siddha medicine from authentic text books.**RESULTS:**Modern Medicine is well Developed System of Medicine ,more Needed Medicine all over the world . At the same time siddha system of Medicine is unique One ,its Fundamentals ,treatment methods are different form modern Medicine .but it has wild books and specific Medicines and treatment , it can be cured from Root of the course . **CONCLUSION:**this developed medicine pushed Siddha medicine downplayed it as alternative medicine. So Siddha medicine is Need to prove scientifically and clinically through the research .

Key words: Modern medicine, Siddha medicine, , Surgery, Herbal, External medicines, internal medicines

INTRODUCTION

Medicine is the art and science of treating diseases. It can be described as the science or activity that helps in diagnosing, treating, and preventing diseases. The rise and dominance of modern medicine began in the 1800s in Western countries such as the United States, Canada, and Europe. At that time, there was no such thing as general medicine, but many medical disciplines.

At that time, there were no solid theories such as the Germ theory of disease, antibiotics, or genetics. There were no standardized methods for diagnosing and treating disease. This situation began to change in the late 1800s. Allopathic medicine was the mainstream medicine at that time. Those doctors formed an association and took action for their own benefit. They either belittled the other groups of the time or brought their own controls.

In the 1900s, medical education was standardized through the work of medical unions, and it became law that medicine was a profession that required licensure. Private colleges were started and medicine rapidly developed into a business.

Only after this did medicine become more scientifically oriented, giving importance to education and work. Scientific studies led to many advances in the study of diseases, methods of diagnosis, and methods of treatment. After the scientificization of medicine, many sub-disciplines emerged. For example, physiotherapy, occupational therapy, x-ray technology, nursing, and pharmacy.

Furthermore, this developed medicine pushed other pre-scientific medical systems such as Siddha medicine and Chinese medicine behind, or downplayed them as alternative medicine. In the early 1900s, medical education and the medical profession were largely in the hands of private businesses. This situation began to change in Canada and many European countries after the 1950s. The private healthcare sector did not meet the medical needs of a large number of people. It had the characteristic of curing diseases after they occur, rather than

preventing them before they occur for profit. This led the majority of the people to demand that the government help provide medical services.

As an extension of this, in the 1960s, Canada and some European countries began to provide medical education and services primarily through the government. After medicine came under government control, doctors were considered government servants.

Modern medicine uses health sciences, biomedicine, biomedical research, and medical technology to diagnose and treat injuries and diseases. This type of treatment is often done through medications, surgery, and other treatments. While medical technology and expertise are essential to modern medicine, understanding human emotions and compassion continue to be essential to reducing the real suffering of patients.

Ancient medicine existed before modern medicine, and was unique to that society. Prehistoric medicine included plants, animal organs, and minerals. Medical anthropology studies various prehistoric medical systems and their interactions with society. Learn from Sangam medical methods. Ancient medical systems include Siddha medicine of the Indian subcontinent, Ayurvedic medicine, ancient Egyptian medicine, and traditional Chinese medicine.

METHODOLOGY

This study compiles data on modern medicine and Siddha medicine from authentic text books for the understanding and validation of the collected information. Reputed journals and Database were referred. **LITERATURE REVIEW**

Ancient Greek medicine is seen as a form of medicine provided by ancient American inhabitants (Mayans, Native Americans)

The ancient Greek physicians Hippocrates and Galen laid the foundation for the later development of rational medicine.

Methods used in the pre-scientific era are still used today, either in addition to or as an alternative to scientific medicine. They are called traditional or alternative medicine or alternative medicine. The universal sacred scripture, Tirukkural, has mentioned about medical concepts.

The disease-causing nadi is the nadi that cures the disease. The mouth-cadi is the action of the mouth. Tirukkural; 948

The amount of time, the amount of pain, and the time The action of the learner. Thirukkural; 949

**நோய்நாடிநோய்முதல்நாடிஅதுதணிக்கும்
வாய்நாடிவாய்ப்பச்செயல். திருக்குறள்; 948
உற்றான் அளவும்பிணியளவும்காலமும்
கற்றான்கருதிச்செயல். திருக்குறள்; 949**

There are major divisions in medicine, including basic medical sciences, specialized medicine, and multidisciplinary medicine. Basic science divisions help to study the causes of diseases in a more detailed manner and to cure the disease. Cytology - The science of cells, the basic unit of life. This field of study (or cell biology) helps in oncology and in understanding cell-based diseases. Genetics - provides knowledge about genes, how they are passed down through generations, and what their role is. Histology - The study of the structure of living tissues using various types of microscopes and immunohistochemistry. Immunology - provides knowledge about the functioning of the immune system in living organisms. Microbiology - The science of the effects, control, toxicity, pharmacology, and medical treatment of disease-causing microorganisms such as bacteria, viruses, fungi, and protozoa. Molecular biology - a branch of biochemistry concerned with the functioning of living molecules (DNA replication, RNA transcription, translation (biology), protein and genetics). Neurology - The study of the nervous system. The physiology of the brain and spinal cord. The basic science of neurosurgery, diseases, and psychology.

Psychology - The science of mental functions and behavior. Nutritional Science - The science that helps to understand the nutrition, digestion, assimilation, essential nutrients for a healthy body and the diseases related to their deficiencies. Pharmacology - The science of drugs and their actions and functions. Nutritional Science - The science that helps to understand the

nutrition, digestion, assimilation, essential nutrients for a healthy body and the diseases related to their deficiencies. Pharmacology - The science of drugs and their actions and functions. Photobiology - The science of the changes that non-ionizing radiation (infrared rays, radio waves, microwaves) causes in the bodies of living organisms. Physiology - The science of the daily movement of body organs. Radiobiology - the science of the biological uses and effects of ionizing radiation. Pathology - is the science of diseases, their causes, infections, and pathogens. The ever-changing nature of drug resistance and the updating of new studies underscore the importance of specialized medicine. After basic medical education, specialized medical training is pursued by practicing doctors. In addition to general medicine, there are also specialized medical and surgical departments.

Trained doctors need to learn more about these specialized medical fields. Surgical medicine, Organ-based (or) therapeutic specialty, Age-specific specialty, Pathology (or) treatment of disease are the types of specialty medicine. Surgery is considered a specialty. The subspecialties of surgery are: Cardiac surgery, Orthopedic surgery, Gastrointestinal surgery, Renal surgery, Otolaryngology, Cancer Surgery, General Surgery, Obstetric Surgery, Transplant Surgery, Plastic Surgery, Vascular Surgery, Trauma Surgery. However, anesthesia is a part of surgery. Cardiology - Specialization of heart diseases (heart attack, heart failure), Gastroenterology, Hematology - Specialization of blood vessels, Nephrology, Neurology, Pulmonology, Ophthalmology, Dentistry, Orthopedics, and Surgical Specialties, Pediatrics, Geriatrics, Age-specific medicine, Pathology, Lifesaving pharmacology - emergency and medical care, Infectious diseases, Oncology

Types of Multidisciplinary Medicine, Emergency Care, Biomedical Engineering, Veterinary Medicine, Tourism Medicine, Defense Medicine, Forensic Medicine, Hospital and Palliative Medicine, Pathology, Evolutionary Medicine, Sexual Medicine, Gender-Based Medicine, Disaster Medicine, Addiction Treatment, Medical Informatics, Laser Medicine, Pain Management, Wilderness Medicine, Sports Medicine.

Traditional medicine is a medical science that has been passed down through generations through knowledge, skills, beliefs, experience, and culture. In this, the traditional medicine of the Tamils called Siddhamaruthuvam is used in South India and the northern and eastern parts of Sri Lanka. Siddhamaruthuvam, Siddha medicine is a South Indian Tamil medical system. Siddha medicine is a system of medicine taught in Tamil by Siddhas in traditional medicine. It is a Tamil medical system compiled by eighteen Siddhas under the guidance of Agasthiyar. The Siddhas have understood it well and have explained it very precisely through their experience. It is impossible to say precisely when Siddha medicine originated. It has spread through traditional traditions. The doshas are divided into three categories: Vata, Pitta, and Kapha. Changes in these three doshas are considered as diseases.

Siddha Medicines Classification of Siddha Medicines: Herbal - Medicines made from plant leaves and stems, Minerals - Medicines made from minerals (salt, water, metal, resin, sulfur) Jivam (a) Sangamam - Medicines made from by-products extracted from animals. The Navaratnam, Navalokas, Rasam are made from the countless herbs, herbs, trees, plants, vines, roots, bark, leaves, flowers, shoots, fruits, seeds, etc. available in nature.

With mineral materials such as sulfur, camphor, tar, iron, coral, etc., and with shellfish such as conch, clam, crab, etc. Trikaduku, Trisathi, Triphala, Baspam, Senthuram, tablets, bandages, powders, bath oils, decoctions, etc. are used for various diseases in various categories, such as good water, sea water, spring water, well water. It is a medical system created with various types of water, such as milk, honey, sugar, ghee, etc., and vegetable oils such as coconut, fenugreek, fenugreek, neem, and sesame.

Siddha medicine does not stop with Siddha medicine. Siddha medicine encompasses the knowledge, science, physical philosophy, religion, astrology, Panchapatsi, string, medicine, medicine, remedy, etc. that excel in Siddha medicine. There is evidence of basic medical principles in Sangam literature. Astrology, Panchapakshi, Tulangiya, Saranul, Margam, Godaru,

Vakara, Vidhai, Gurumuni, Othu, Padal, Didhilak, Kakkidangal, Seppiya, Kanma, Kandan, Itelaam.

These learned men are the doctors..... (-- SiddharNadi Book 18 --)The human body is divided into three types. The elements that sustain life in the physical body are: Vata (air), Pitta (heat), Silethumam (water), and chime (rasadatu). Our intake foods are covered to Blood(இரத்ததாது), Muscles(மாமிசதாது), Fat (மேதோதாது), Bone (அஸ்திதாது), Bone Marrow(மச்சைதாது), semen,ovamசுக்கிலதாதுFeces(மலம்), Urine(மூத்திரம்)above The twelve elements are separated from the food we eat and provide strength and movement.

The food that is eaten is the water that is eaten - Purananuru,18"The food we eat is the medicine that keeps our body alive. Diseases are caused by eating foods that are not suitable for our body and that are not in the right way.The three elements of air, heat, and doubt in our body, whether present in excess or in deficiency, can cause disease. These are divided into Vata, pitta, and kapha diseases.

Vata -related diseasesThere are eighty diseases mainly related to Vata . These include neuralgia, neuralgia, epilepsy, stroke, gas, blood pressure, heart disease, etc. The land of Neithal, which is a sea and maritime area, is prone to arthritis-related diseases.

Diseases related to bileThere are forty diseases mainly related to bile. Indigestion, stomach pain, stomach ulcer, jaundice, anemia, hematemesis These include diseases such as liver and gallbladder damage. Fields and fields, which are fertile lands, are prone to diseases related to bile.

Diseases related to sylhet,Ninety-six diseases are important in sylhet. These include runny nose, nasal congestion, congestion, cough, wheezing, and asthma.Regarding the method of

avoiding diseases, Thirukkural says, "If you do not need medicine, eat what is not eaten." (If you only eat foods that are said to be non-diseasing, you don't need any medicine.)

Medicine

There are 64 forms of medicine in Siddha medicine, 32 internal medicines and 32 external medicines. It is considered a medicine for stomach diseases. Denial is the medicine for the disease of death. Rejection is the medicine for the disease of death

(-- Thirumoolar Thirumanthiram --) According to Thirumula Siddha, medicine is not only about curing diseases of the body and mind, but also about preventing diseases from occurring. And it should also prevent death from occurring. Such medicines are widely found in Siddha medicine.

The internal medicines and their shelf life are as follows:

“உள்மருந்துகரசஞ்சாறுகுடிநீர்கற்கம்
உட்களிஅடைஓர்சாமம்
உயர்தூரணம்பிட்டுவடகம்வெண்ணெய்நான்கின்
உயிர்மூன்றுதிங்களாகும்
விள்மணப்பாகுநெய்இரசாயனம்இளகம்நால்
மேவும்அறுதிங்கள்எண்ணெய்
விரலிடும்உயர்ந்தமாத்திரைகடுகுபக்குவம்
மிளிறும் தேனூறல்தீநீர்
கொள்ளாறும்ஓராண்டுமெழுகோடுகுழம்புஜந்து
கோப்பதங்கம்பத்தாகும்
குருதிபொடிஎழுபானோடுஐந்தாண்டுநீறுகட்டு
உருக்குகளங்குநானூறு
எள்ளிடாச்சுண்ணம்ஐநூறுகற்பம்சத்து
குருகுளிகைமிக்கஆயுள்ளன்று
எவரும்மகிழ்ச்சித்தர்முப்பத்திரண்டகமருந்து

இசைத்தவராய் உள்ளனவரோ”

(சித்த மருத்துவமும் சித்தர் தத்தவமும்)

அகமருந்துகளும், அவற்றின் எடுத்துக்காட்டுகளும்:

- 1.சுரசம் - இஞ்சிசுரசம் 2.சாறு - கற்றாழைச்சாறு 3.குடிநீர் - ஆடாதோடைக்குடிநீர் 4.கற்கம் -கீழாநெல்லிக்கற்கம் 5.உட்களி -கடுகு உட்களி6.அடை - தூதுவளைஅடை 7.சூரணம் - அமுக்கிராச்சூரணம் 8.பிட்டு 9.வடகம் -தாளிசாதி வடகம்10.வெண்ணெய்- குங்கிலிய வெண்ணெய்11.மணப்பாகு - மாதுளை மணப்பாகு12.நெய் - ஆடாதோடைநெய்13.இரசாயனம் - இஞ்சிஇரசாயனம்14.இளகம்- கேசரிஇளகம்15.எண்ணெய்- பூரஎண்ணெய் 16.மாத்திரை-பாலசஞ்சீவி மாத்திரை 17.கடுகு -18.பக்குவம்- பாவனக்கடுக்காய் 19.தேனூறல் -இஞ்சி20.தீநீர்- ஓமம்21.மெழுகு - கிளிஞ்சல் மெழுகு22.குழம்பு- சாதிஜம்பீரக்குழம்பு23.பதங்கம் -சாம்பிராணிப்பதங்கம்24.செந்துாரம்- இரசசெந்துாரம்25.நீறு அல்லதுபற்பம்- முத்துப்பற்பம்26.கட்டு- இரசக்கட்டு 27.உருக்கு -28.களங்கு 29.சுண்ணம்- வெடியுப்பச்சுண்ணம்30.கற்பம் 31.சத்து- கடுக்காய் சத்து32.குருகுளிகை- இரசமணி

External or topical medications and their shelf life are as follows:

“வெளிமருந்தேகட்டுபற்றுஒற்றடம்பூச்சு

வேதுபொட்டணம்தொக்கணம்

மென்புகைமைபொடிதிமிர்தல்கலிக்கம்நசியம்ஊதல்

மேவுநாசிகாபரணமும்

களிம்புசீலைநீர்வர்த்திசுட்டிகைசலாகைபசை

களிபொடிமுறிச்சல்கீறல்

காரம்அட்டைஅறுவைகொம்புறிஞ்சல்குருதி

கண்டுவாங்குதல்பீச்சுஇவை

வெளிமருந்துமுப்பத்திரண்டென்றுகூறினார்

விண்ணுலவுசித்தராமால்
மேல்வர்த்தியும்புகைபீச்சுமைநசியமும்
மென்கலிக்கங்கள்ஓராண்டு
ஒளிவர்த்திபொடிநீர்நாசிகாபரணம்இவை
ஒருமுன்றுதிங்களாகும்
உயர்சீலைகளிம்புஇவைகள் ஆறுதிங்கள் ஆகுமென்று
ஓதினாராய்உளருமரோ”
(சித்த மருத்துவமும் சித்தர் தத்தவமும்)

வெளிஅல்லதுபுறமருந்துகள்:

1.கட்டு -

இலைகள் அல்லது பட்டைகளை நைய இடித்தோ அரைத்தோ வதக்கியோ புளித்த நீர் முதலியவற்றில் வேகவைத்தோ கட்டுதல்

2.பற்று-

சரக்குகளை நீர்மப் பொருள் விட்டு அரைத்து சுடவைத்தோ சுடவைக்காமலோ நோயுள்ள இடங்களில் அப்புதல்

3.ஒற்றடம்-

சரக்குகளை சூடுபடுத்தித் துணியில் முடிந்து நோயுள்ள இடங்களில் ஒற்றுதல்

4.பூச்சு-

நீர்மப் பொருட்கள் மற்றும் பசை குழம்பு நிலையில் உள்ளவற்றை நோயுள்ள இடங்களில் பூசுதல்

5.வேது-

சரக்குகளை எடுத்துக் கொதிக்க வைத்து அதனின்று எழும் ஆவியை நவது வாரங்களில் ஏதாவது ஒன்றின் வழியாக இழுத்தல்

6.பொட்டணம்-

சரக்குகளைத் துணியில் முடிந்துச் சுடவைத்த நெய்ப்புப் பொருட்களில் நனைத்து நோயுள்ள இடங்களில் ஒற்றடமிடுதல்

7.தொக்கணம்-

இது மர்த்தனம் எனப்படும். இது வெறுங்கையால் பிடிப்பதும் தைலங்களைத் தடவிப் பிடிப்பதும் என இரு வகைப்படும்.

8.புகை-

சரக்குகளை நெருப்பிலிட்டு எழும்புகையைப் பிடித்தல் அல்லது குடித்தல் அல்லது புண் முதலியவற்றுக்குத் தாக்கும் படிசெய்தல்.

9.மை-

உ-ம் நீலாஞ்சனமை

10.பொடிதிமிர்தல்-

உடம்பில் தேய்த்து உருட்டி உதிர்த்தல் உ-ம் மஞ்சள் பொடி

11.கலிக்கம் -

சில சரக்குகளைச் சில சாறுகளால் அரைத்த உருட்டி மாத்திரையாக்கி தேனிலாவது வேறு சாற்றிலாவது உரைத்துக் கண்ணில் போடுதல்

12.நசியம்-

இலைச்சாறு அல்லது தைலம் அல்லது மாத்திரைகளைத் தாய்ப்பாலுடன் உரைத்து முக்கிலிடுதல்

13.ஊதல்-

(ஆக்கிராணம்) சரக்குகளை வாயிலிட்டு மென்று காது முதலியவற்றில் ஊதல்.

14.நாசிகாபரணம்-

சரக்குகளை இடித்து முக்கிலிடுவது

15.களிம்பு-

உ-ம் வங்க விரணக் களிம்பு வங்கக் களிம்பு

16.சீலை-

- குழம்பில் துணித்தண்டை தோய்த்து விரணங்களுக்கு உபயோகிப்பது
- 17.நீர்-
விரணங்களைக் கழுவுவதற்கு உபயோகிக்கும் நீர்மப்பொருட்கள்
- 18.வர்த்தி -
ஆறாத விரணங்களுக்கும் புரையோடும் விரணங்களுக்கும் வைப்பது
- 19.சுட்டிகை -
சுடு கை எனப்படும்
- 20.சலாகை-
கட்டிகள் புரைகள் சிலைப் புண் பவுத்திரம் போன்றவற்றின் நோய் நிலைமையை அறிய உதவும் உலோகக்கருவிகள்
- 21.பசை -
உ-ம் கார்போகிப்பசை
- 22.களி -
நீர்விட்டு அரைத்த சரக்குகளைக் கரண்டியிலிட்டு சுடவைத்தோ
சுடவைக்காமலோ கட்டுதல்
- 23.பொடி -
சரக்குகளைப் பொடித்து எடுத்து கொள்ளுதல்
- 24.முறிச்சல் -
எலும்புகள் பிறழ்ந்து இருந்தால் அதனைச் சரியான நிலைக்கு மாற்றுதல்
- 25.கீறல் -
கட்டி பரு கொப்புளம் ஆகியவற்றில் தங்கியுள்ள சீழ் இரத்தம் நீர் என்பவற்றை நீக்க கீறிவிடல்
- 26.காரம் -
விரணத்தை ஆற்றுவதற்காகத் தோற்றவிப்பதற்காகப் பயன்படுத்தப்படும் சில நச்சு மருந்துகளும் அதன் கட்டுகளும்

27. அட்டை விடல்-

நோயுற்று வீங்கின இடங்களில் தீய இரத்தத்தை அகற்றுவதற்காக அட்டைவிடல்

28. அறுவை-

தேவையில்லாதவற்றை அறுத்து நீக்கி தைத்து செம்மைப்படுத்தல்

29. கொம்பு கட்டல் -

உடைந்த உறுப்புக்களை இணைத்து மீண்டும் ஒட்டும்படி மரச்சட்டம் கட்டிவடல்.

30. உறிஞ்சல் -

விரணங்களிலுள்ள சீழ் குருதி என்பவற்றை உறிஞ்சி எடுத்தல்.

31. குருதி வாங்குதல்-

இரத்தக்குழாயைக் கீறி இரத்தத்தை வெளிப்படுத்தல்.

32. பீச்சு-

மலம் வெளிப்படாவிடில் குழாய் மூலமாக நீர்மப்பொருட்களை உட்செலுத்துதல்

(சித்த மருத்துவமும் சித்தர் தத்தவமும்)

Test

Vatma, Pitta and Kapha are the three sources of diseases. The test method suggested by the Siddhas to check whether there is a lot of disease in the body. Take a little water in a glass vessel in the morning. Put a drop of essential oil in it. Then observe how it reacts.

If the oil drop is curved like a snake, arthritis is increasing in the body. If it is round like a ring, there is gallstone disease. If it stands like a pearl, it means that you have a Kapha-related disease. Also, if the oil drop spreads quickly, the disease will be cured soon, if it spreads slowly, it will be delayed, and if it remains the same, the disease will not be cured. If a drop of oil is scattered or submerged, it cannot cure the disease.

RESULTS: modern Medicine has new technology advanced study Methods(embryology) , well designed advanced tools and instruments for diagnosis (MRI,C-tscan) Early Diagnosis methods for cell level changes(biopsy)and ect .it has well known pharmacological methods medicines. And the Siddha Medicine classified 4448 Diseases and has unique diagnosis methods Attavithaparidchi(8 Methods) Naadiparidchi is one of it (use tindex ,middle,ring three fingers and palpate the patient's wrist region.)

CONCLUSION: this developed medicine pushed Siddha medicine downplayed it as alternative medicine. So Siddha medicine is Need to prove scientifically and clinically through the research . Scientific systematization and standardization The treatments and prescriptions recommended in Siddha medicine are scientifically and clinically proven.The Central Government Centre for Siddha Medicine Research has also been involved in the process of developing and testing the D 5 Sooranam for diabetes and the 777 Oil for the treatment of skin diseases.Thus, they have been clinically tested and patented.

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